

Assessment of Carbon-Dioxide Emission from Non-Road Equipment Construction Sources at a Flyover Development Site in Port Harcourt, Nigeria

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Abstract:

It is emphasized that global warming and climate change vary directly with the increase in the concentration of greenhouse gases, particularly carbon dioxide across domains. The constructions of social and economic infrastructures in developing counties such as Nigeria at a higher rate increases the emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) into the lower atmosphere. Non-road construction equipment sources powered by fossil fuels are considered to be primary emitters of greenhouse gases during the construction stages of large infrastructure project. In this study, inventory of non-road construction machinery emissions from the Tank junction flyover construction site along East-West Road in Port Harcourt

metropolis were estimated via field data gathering. Results showed that an average of about 398.7 g/s (4134.4 ton/year) of CO₂ is released from the construction site in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Among the various types of non-road engines considered, the mobile crane was the largest single contributor to the total CO₂ emissions, accounting for 18.5%. Machinery with power above 300 kW were 8 out of 30 equipment on site and accounted for the largest share (52.87%) of total CO₂ emissions. Based on the findings from current research literature and the case study, control strategies such as enforcing standards and policy, conducting impact assessment, adopting low carbon technology, and restricting energy utilization need to be implemented in other reduce the impact of global warming and alleviate climate change. Therefore, CO₂ emission mitigation plans and schemes are necessary alongside standardized frameworks and guidelines. All stakeholders must play their roles efficiently to reduce CO₂ emissions and aid in mitigating the effects of climate change.

Keywords: *Carbon dioxide, Emission Factor, Non-Road Emission Sources, Construction Machinery, Carbon Footprint.*

Introduction

The increasing average earth's atmospheric temperature has led to global warming, which drives a set of changes to the earth's climate and weather systems as humans continue to emit heat-trapping greenhouse gases (GHG) into the atmosphere (Alhorr et al., 2014; Mardiana, 2015). It is well-known that CO₂ emissions contribute to global warming and climate change, which can significantly cause severe impacts and consequences for humans and the environment. Klufallah (2014) disclosed that CO₂ emissions act like a blanket in the air, trapping heat in the atmosphere and warming up the Earth. This layer prevents the Earth from cooling and thus raises global temperature. The built environment is the anthropogenic surroundings that provide infrastructure and facilities for human activities, and they are the fundamental components of the economy and social development of a nation (Yan, 2010). The acceleration of urbanization plays a considerable role in rising CO₂ emissions despite urbanization being a dynamic process that changes rural areas into urban areas (Sepasgozar & Blair, 2019). Rao & Rao (2006) evaluated that urbanization and the dependence on internal combustion engines have over time increased the concentration of gaseous and particulate emissions in cities.

Non-road sources, in most cases, known as Non-Road Mobile Machinery (NRMM) cover a variety of equipment that is used in different economic sectors and is typified as all machinery equipped with a combustion engine which is not primarily intended for transport on public roads and which is not attached to a stationary unit (Kean, et al., 2000). These non-road equipment sources are driven by devices that burn fossil fuels from the internal combustion that takes place and according to Obert (1973), the process of internal combustion, the ignition of the air-fuel mixture generates gaseous and particulate emissions and when at limits above regulatory standards, poses negative cumulative impacts on the ambient air quality. The non-road construction machinery used in the development of infrastructure contributes a

significant portion of greenhouse gas and air pollution during construction works such as site preparation, foundation works, road construction and maintenance (Zolfagharian et al., 2012). Recently, non-road mobile sources have attracted increasing attention because of their increasing contribution to air pollution and climate change (McDonald et al., 2015; Campbell et al., 2018). The energy sourced from fossil fuels is non-sustainable and accounts for a large percentage of the energy used in the construction and operation processes. Renewable energy sources only account for 6% of the total energy used in the construction sector, while fossil fuel used in construction activities accounts for 40% of worldwide greenhouse gas emissions (Yim, 2018). As one of the significant pollution and emission sources, heavy construction equipment, powered by diesel engines, emits toxic pollutants including CO, NO_x, HC, and particulate matter, as well as CO₂. (Xue et al., 2021). It has been estimated that emissions of NO_x and PM from construction machinery in 2020 in China accounted for 31.3% and 32.5% of the total non-road mobile source emissions of NO_x and PM, respectively (MEE, 2021). Therefore, the emissions of gaseous and particulate pollutants, including hydrocarbons (HCs), carbon monoxide (CO), NO_x, PM and CO₂ from construction machinery should be quantified to improve air quality and alleviate climate change. In their emission inventory for Tianjin, in China Zhang et al. (2021) showed that forklifts, excavators and loaders contributed the most to air pollutant emissions, accounting for approximately 70% of emissions from non-road construction machinery. Guo et al. (2020) stated that although the effect of climate change is analyzed, the release of the principal gases associated with this phenomenon will remain cogent largely due to the continuous anthropogenic releases. It is a difficult task to estimate the accurate amount of emissions due to a lack of measurement and monitoring information. Emissions can only be currently measured based on specified emission rates,

modified by load factors, operating time, equipment deterioration, etc.

Studies on the causes and effects of air pollution have necessitated the need for emission inventories, emission modelling, land use control, impact on health, economic and environmental strategies for pollution prevention and alternative fuels. This paper evaluates emissions from non-road equipment construction sites for infrastructural development in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, with a view to determining the non-road equipment emissions as emissions from non-road sources such as generators in Port Harcourt, Nigeria where earlier evaluated by Ede and Oriji (2013). This estimated emission aims to provide an overview of the issues, impacts, and mitigation strategies in the construction sector to reduce and control CO₂ emissions (Ma et al., 2019).

Materials and Methods

This study assessed the carbon footprint from an inventory of non-road mobile sources at the Tank Junction Flyover construction site along the East-West Road, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Primary data for source inventory were obtained by direct observation from the field, and through

appropriately designed questionnaires that were administered at the project site, augmented with interviews. The basic data needed to compute and allocate emission estimates are the emission factors, base year equipment population, activity, load factor, average lifetime, scrappage function, growth estimates, and geographic and temporal allocation. Details of the selected equipment like engine characteristics, and number of actual working hours of the equipment per day and idle hours per day were noted for 30 days.

Equipment Inventory

The classifications of non-road equipment will impact the difficulties in developing emission inventory and its accuracy. In order to classify the non-road equipment for emissions inventory development, the data availability for population, activity, and emission factor for each class of non-road equipment was taken into account. The data collected from the construction site includes equipment population for the base year, average load factor expressed as average fraction of available power, available power in horsepower, fuel type, activity in hours of use per year and emission factor with deterioration and/or new standards. number of hours of each piece of equipment is tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. Inventory of Non- Road Machinery at Construction Site

Equipment Type	Activity (Hours/Year)	Fuel Type	Engine Power (Hp)	Number of Engine	Cumulative Power (Hp)	Kilo Watt	Mega watt	mmbtu/hr
Mobile cranes	2928	Diesel	469.4	3	1408	350.0	0.3500	1.1943
Excavator	2928	Diesel	128	3	384	95.4	0.0954	0.3257
Forklift	2928	Diesel	109	1	109	81.3	0.0813	0.2773
Backhoe	2928	Diesel	78	2	156	58.2	0.0582	0.1985
Wheel loaders	2928	Diesel	200	3	600	149.1	0.1491	0.5089
Skid steer loaders	2928	Diesel	70	2	140	52.2	0.0522	0.1781
Off highway trucks	2928	Diesel	435	5	2175	324.4	0.3244	1.1068
Compact track loader	2928	Diesel	67	2	134	50.0	0.0500	0.1705
Asphalt Mixer	2928	Diesel	450	1	450	335.6	0.3356	1.1449
Tire roller	2928	Diesel	400	1	400	298.3	0.2983	1.0177
Drum roller	2928	Diesel	100	1	100	74.6	0.0746	0.2544
Grader	2928	Diesel	290	4	1160	216.3	0.2163	0.7379
Asphalt Paver	2928	Diesel	146	1	146	108.9	0.1089	0.3715
Generator	2928	Diesel	266.7	1	267	198.9	0.1989	0.6786

Emission Factor

The emission factor is the average emission rate of a given source, relative to units of activity or process/processes. The emission factors of the non-road mobile source were the average emission coefficients recommended by USEPA 1999 (Table 2). The quantity of pollutant released with an activity associated generates an emission factor as cited by MEP (2014), Geng (2017) and Kean et al. (2000).

Table 2. CO₂ Emission Factors for Non-Road Mobile Source for Diesel and Petrol Engines

Engine Capacity	CO ₂	
	Diesel	Petrol
<600hp	163.05	154.81
>600hp	163.05	154.81

Source: USEPA 1999

The emission rate for CO₂ emission in lb/hr was determined from equation 1 given as:

$$\text{Emission rate} = \text{Heat Input or Power Output (MMBtu/hr)} \times \text{Emission Factor} \quad (1)$$

where: lb/hr = Pounds per hour

The conversion rate from lb/hr to g/s is given by:

$$1 \text{ lb/hr} = 0.12599 \text{ g/s} \quad (2)$$

Emission rate in (ton/yr) is given by:

$$\text{Emissions (lb/hr)} \times \text{operating hours (hr/yr)} \times \frac{1 \text{ lb}}{2,000 \text{ tons}} \quad (3)$$

Assumptions and Limitations

The uncertainty in this research originates primarily from the estimation of the population of non-road equipment, acquisition of activity data, and selection of actual emission factors. With regard to the estimation of the population of non-road equipment, Nigeria has not yet established a relevant registration and filing system for non-road equipment, and there are differences in statistics obtained and observed. The lack of an extensive database of activity and emissions for non-road equipment reduced the certainty associated with these factors and thus reduced the accuracy of emission inventory development. Unsuccessful emission inventory for the construction site is due to factors which are difficult to quantify their degree of impact on the rate of emissions and to measure. The factors as prescribed in USEPA (2005) can be categorized into four groups such as equipment condition (make, year, model, size, engine power, engine rebuild, fuel quality, technology assessment), equipment maintenance (routine maintenance, running repair), operating condition (job nature, job site condition, environmental conditions, altitude) and equipment operations (idling, control, operator skills, equipment selection, deployment, equipment operation and Planning).

Results and Discussions

This section mainly presents the status of research in emission inventory for non-road equipment at the tank flyover construction site. In this study, construction machinery was classified by equipment types, population, rated power and emission standards in order to facilitate emission estimates. The horsepower (HP) of each piece of equipment was used to calculate the emissions in grams per second. Table 3 shows the estimated emission rates of pollutants for the various machinery sources from the construction site under scrutiny in this study. Results show that an average total of 398.7 g/s and 4633.4 ton/year of CO₂ is released from a construction site in

Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The mobile crane is the highest average producer of CO₂ emissions followed by the Asphalt mixer and the off-highway trucks. There are other anthropogenic sources of CO₂ emitted into the atmosphere such as biomass burnings, electricity generation sets, indiscriminate burnings of oil and gas products, vehicular emissions as well as other oil and gas refineries located in the Niger Delta areas of Nigeria. These additional sources also contribute considerably to CO₂ emissions in Nigeria.

Table 3. Estimated Emission Rate

Non-Road Equipment	CO ₂ Emissions	
	g/sec	Tons/year
Mobile cranes	73.6	855.3
Excavator	20.1	233.2
Forklift	5.7	66.2
Backhoe	8.2	94.8
Wheel loaders	31.4	364.4
Skid steer loaders	7.3	85.0
Off highway trucks	113.7	1320.9
Compact track loader	7.0	81.4
Asphalt Mixer	23.5	273.3
Tire roller	20.9	242.9
Drum roller	5.2	60.7
Grader	60.6	704.5
Asphalt Paver	7.6	88.7
Generator	13.9	161.9
TOTAL	398.7	4633.4

Conclusion

The overarching purpose of this study was to contribute to this important theme of a quality environment with particular emphasis on emissions from a construction site with a lot of similar sites located in Port Harcourt which is in the environmentally fragile Niger Delta area of Nigeria. In order to attain the ultimate level of industrialization for improved economic and sustainable development, developing nations such as Nigeria will continue to create the required pressure of reaching the desired goal. As the economy continues to develop, additional CO₂ emissions will be released into the atmosphere due to the avoidance of adaptive

techniques in reducing the emissions. According to Aye et al. (2017), economic development and preserving the environment are the two major challenges facing humanity. Therefore, the concern of the developing countries like Nigeria that mitigating CO₂ emissions will jeopardize the economy will only continue to make the environment less important and susceptible to the devastating effects of climate change (Edokpa & Ede, 2018). The findings from the study indicate that significant emissions of pollutants come from the use of diesel construction machinery. The air quality of the city will get worse assuming a steady growth in the economy, and contributions from other sources are introduced into the calculation. The tremendous production and release of CO₂ have led to severe consequences and repercussions contributing to climate change. The strategies to reduce CO₂ in the construction sector are enforcing standards and policy, conducting impact assessments, adopting low-carbon technology, and restricting energy utilization (Lewis et al., 2009). The future of sustainable cities and communities will remain uncertain, and we might fail to achieve global sustainable development goals. Environmental managers in the country should begin to consider inventorying every emission source and stipulate standards as long-term measures. The construction sector must be given enough attention and care to reduce the rate of CO₂ emissions. For a more sustainable future, it is crucial to implement drastic actions and measures to reduce CO₂ emissions to aid the fight against climate change.

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